

Stability Constants of Biligand Chelates of Lanthanum(III) and Neodymium(III) with NTA, HEDTA, EDTA, CYDTA and DTPA as Primary Ligands and Aromatic Dihydroxy Compounds as Secondary Ligands

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THE biligand chelates of rare earths with multi-dentate ligands such as complexons¹⁻³ have been reported and in some cases an expansion in the coordination number have been suggested.

In continuation with our earlier work^{4,5} we describe in the present paper a pH-metric study of the formation of biligand complexes of lanthanum(III) and neodymium(III) with NTA, HEDTA, EDTA, CYDTA and DTPA as primary ligands and alizarin red-S (ARS), hydroquinone (HQ) and raseacetophenone sulphonic acid (RAPSA) as secondary ligands at 25, 35 and 45° and at a fixed ionic strength ($\mu=0.1 M$, KNO_3). The thermodynamic parameters have also been evaluated and discussed.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. Experimental details pertaining to determining the stability constants of 1 : 1 : 1 biligand chelates were similar to those described earlier⁶.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS (KH), METAL-LIGAND CONSTANTS (K_{MAL}^M) AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS*

System*	$\mu = 0.1 M (KNO_3)$, Temp. = 35°			$-\Delta G$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H$ kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	$\log KH/\log K_{MAL}^M$	25°	35°			
H ₂ RAPSA (sodium salt)	11.96 4.50	18.82 4.42	11.68 ^a 3.94 ^b	—	—	—
H ₂ ARS	11.09 5.60	11.05 5.56	11.01 ^a 5.52 ^b	—	—	—
H ₂ HQ	11.42 6.82	11.36 6.77	11.31 ^a 6.71 ^b	—	—	—
[La ^{III} -NTA-RAPSA]	5.46	5.10	4.92	7.2	2.5	15.2
[La ^{III} -HEDTA-RAPSA]	5.26	4.94	4.70	7.0	2.5	14.7
[La ^{III} -EDTA-RAPSA]	5.02	4.91	4.82	7.0	4.4	8.3
[La ^{III} -CYDTA-RAPSA]	4.92	4.76	4.52	6.7	3.7	9.7
[La ^{III} -DTPA-RAPSA]	4.81	4.62	4.33	6.5	3.8	8.9
[Nd ^{III} -NTA-RAPSA]	6.40	6.16	5.92	8.7	4.2	14.7
[Nd ^{III} -HEDTA-RAPSA]	5.88	5.54	5.08	7.7	3.4	14.0
[Nd ^{III} -EDTA-RAPSA]	5.52	5.16	5.02	7.3	3.1	13.7
[Nd ^{III} -CYDTA-RAPSA]	4.98	4.85	4.57	6.8	4.2	8.5
[Nd ^{III} -DTPA-RAPSA]	4.88	4.67	4.39	6.6	3.7	9.3
[La ^{III} -NTA-ARS]	5.54	5.47	5.40	7.7	3.6	11.1
[La ^{III} -HEDTA-ARS]	5.06	4.94	4.86	7.0	4.4	14.2
[La ^{III} -CYDTA-ARS]	4.95	4.83	4.78	6.9	5.9	19.5
[La ^{III} -DTPA-ARS]	4.86	4.81	4.74	6.7	3.7	11.7
[Nd ^{III} -NTA-ARS]	6.30	6.26	6.22	8.9	4.1	12.8
[Nd ^{III} -HEDTA-ARS]	5.72	5.66	5.59	8.0	4.2	13.3
[Nd ^{III} -CYDTA-ARS]	5.10	5.06	5.01	7.2	2.4	7.6
[Nd ^{III} -DTPA-ARS]	5.04	5.01	4.92	7.1	2.6	8.3
[La ^{III} -NTA-HQ]	5.84	5.73	5.67	8.2	3.3	10.5
[La ^{III} -HEDTA-HQ]	5.60	5.56	5.50	7.9	3.4	10.8
[La ^{III} -CYDTA-HQ]	5.55	5.50	5.42	7.8	3.3	10.5
[La ^{III} -DTPA-HQ]	4.79	4.66	4.59	5.9	3.1	10.2
[Nd ^{III} -NTA-HQ]	6.26	6.14	6.03	8.7	3.1	10.0
[Nd ^{III} -HEDTA-HQ]	6.13	6.09	6.05	8.6	2.8	8.9
[Nd ^{III} -CYDTA-HQ]	6.10	6.03	5.86	8.5	3.6	12.7
[Nd ^{III} -DTPA-HQ]	4.88	4.74	4.61	6.0	3.9	12.4

*A = NTA, HEDTA, EDTA, CYDTA and DTPA ; L = ARS, HQ, RAPA.

^alog K_1^H , ^blog K_2^H .

A Systronic-335 digital pH meter with calibrated glass electrode and a saturated calomel separated by salt-bridge to avoid the influence of Cl^- ions, was used for pH measurements. The temperature was maintained by immersing the cell in a thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).

Results and Discussion

The practical proton-ligand constants ($\log K^H$) of ARS, HQ and RAPSA (sodium salt) and metal-ligand constants ($\log K_{MAL}^M$) for 1:1:1 biligand chelates evaluated by using the Irving-Rossotti technique⁷ and extension to biligand system⁸ are summarised in Table 1.

The secondary ligands ARS, HQ and RAPSA are dihydroxy, aromatic compounds. The large difference in the successive deprotonation constants of ARS and HQ was because of the stable quinonide formation due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding⁹. The secondary ligands offered (O, O) bidentate chelation¹⁰. The first step deprotonation of RAPSA probably involved deprotonation of the phenolic OH group at *para*-position to the CH_3CO group and the second step involved the deprotonation of the phenolic OH group at the *ortho*-position to the CH_3CO group as there is possibility of the intramolecular hydrogen bonding between latter OH proton with the carbonyl oxygen atom of the CH_3CO group. The secondary ligand RAPSA may act as bidentate ligand using the carbonyl oxygen of the CH_3CO group and the phenolic oxygen group at its *ortho*-position.

The order $\text{La}^{III} < \text{Nd}^{III}$ of stability constants ($\log K_{MAL}^M$) could be attributed to the decreased size and increased ionic potential of the Nd^{III} ions¹¹. The expansions of coordination sphere of metal ions could take place in case of all primary ligands except NTA. The primary chelate (MNTA) and (MHEDTA) were electrically neutral, MCYDTA and MEDTA were mono-negative and MDTPA was binegative. This lowered electrostatic attraction of MA for the secondary ligands in going from M(NTA), and this results in destabilising the biligand chelates. ΔH and ΔG for the biligand chelate formation were favourable (Table 1). ΔS values were positive, all showing chelation of the (L) with (MA) to form the biligand $[\text{M}(\text{A})-(\text{L})]$ complexes.

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Potentiometric Studies of Metal Schiff Base Chelates in Mixed Aquo-organic Solvent Systems

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LITERATURE survey reveals that the proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation equilibria in mixed solvent systems are greatly influenced by the nature of the co-solvent¹⁻⁵. With an aim to study such effects, we report in this communication, a potentiometric study of the Schiff base ligand salicylidene-2-iminopyridine and the formation of its complexes with rare earth metal ions, Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} , Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} in aquo-organic solvent systems having different dielectric constant values.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were either of A.R grade or purified before use. Double-distilled water was used throughout.

Preparation of ligand: The ligand was prepared by following the method as described in our earlier paper⁶.

Preparation of metal salt solution: Rare earth metals were converted to perchlorates by dissolving their oxides/carbonates with requisite amount of perchloric acid and evaporating it to dryness on a water-bath. The metal ions were estimated by EDTA method. The metal perchlorates were dissolved in 0.1 M HClO_4 to avoid hydrolysis.

pH-titration technique: pH-metric titration method of Bjerrum-Calvin^{5,6} as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁷ was followed to determine the formation constant values. The experimental procedure involved the titration of (i) free acid, (ii) acid + ligand and (iii) acid + ligand + metal ion solutions